

CONSISTENCY AND VARIABILITY IN EXPERIMENTAL HEAT PAIN RESPONSES OVER TIME

David P. Cros

University of Toronto Centre for the Study of Pain, Toronto, Canada

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20160644>

ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>Longitudinal and interventional pain studies require reliable outcome measures. Self-reported pain intensity and phasic heat pain (PHP) unpleasantness are widely used gold-standard measures. Secondary hyperalgesia area elicited by PHP is increasingly used as an outcome measure in experimental pain studies. However, the test-retest reliability and stability of these measures across multiple sessions remain unclear.</p> <p>Twenty-four healthy participants (12 males, 12 females) attended three sessions, each including a familiarization procedure and a PHP calibrated to 50/100 pain intensity. Pain intensity ratings, pain unpleasantness ratings, and the area of secondary hyperalgesia were recorded after PHP. Intraclass correlation coefficients (ICC) indicated good reliability for pain intensity (ICC = 0.755) and secondary hyperalgesia (ICC = 0.840), and moderate reliability for pain unpleasantness (ICC = 0.636). Repeated-measures ANOVA revealed low stability for self-reported pain intensity and unpleasantness across sessions ($p < 0.005$), whereas secondary hyperalgesia showed high stability ($p = 0.296$) supported by Bayesian analysis (BF01 = 3.36). Validation in an independent dataset confirmed moderate reliability for PHP pain intensity (ICC = 0.718).</p> <p>These findings suggest that while all PHP outcome measures show moderate-to-good reliability, only secondary hyperalgesia area remains stable across sessions, highlighting its potential as a robust measure in longitudinal and interventional pain research.</p>	<p>Phasic heat pain (PHP), Pain intensity, Pain unpleasantness, Secondary hyperalgesia, Reliability Stability, Test-retest, Experimental pain, Outcome measures</p>

Introduction

In human pain research, various pain outcome measures can determine interventional efficacy; thus, understanding the reliability and stability of these outcome measures is critical to draw appropriate conclusions. Self-report pain intensity and pain unpleasantness ratings are gold standard measures of the pain experience, given that pain is a subjective experience.¹ Pain ratings captured using a verbal numerical rating scale (vNRS) are among the most common pain outcome measures in acute and chronic pain,²⁻⁴ and previous studies found

the vNRS to have good to excellent reliability.^{3,5–7} Similarly, pain thresholds and pain tolerance show moderate-to-good reliability, but are more reliable in females than males.⁸ However, the overall reliability of these ratings can depend on the pain model utilized and the specific testing Parameters that are employed.^{9,10}

Previous studies that have investigated the reliability of various stimulation paradigms have found variable outcomes, depending on the paradigm employed. For example, one study showed that pain ratings to brief heat stimuli are stable across time, even when challenged by a tonic heat pain stimulus.¹¹ Another study showed that heat pain thresholds and tolerance were moderately reliable, and more reliable in females than males.⁸ Another study of various paradigms showed poor-to-excellent reliability across two sessions, depending on the paradigm employed;¹² notably, dynamic tests were less reliable.

The phasic heat pain (PHP) model is gaining popularity,^{13–15} given the advantages it offers, such as its ability to elicit pain, drive hyperalgesia, reproducibility, and optimality for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). However, the test-retest reliability and stability of pain outcome measures across multiple sessions for PHP in pain-free individuals has yet to be assessed. Should these measures be deemed unstable, this presents a significant challenge to pain research, as the reliability and stability of these measures is central to the interpretation of results.

Another pain outcome measure is secondary hyperalgesia, characterized by increased sensitivity to noxious stimuli in areas surrounding an injury or inflamed site.¹⁶ The area of secondary hyperalgesia is determined based on a change in rating to a noxious mechanical stimulus presented along trajectories radiating toward the primary site, marking the boundary of secondary mechanical hyperalgesia. Therefore, the area of secondary hyperalgesia is based on a composite of self-reported pain elicited by a punctate mechanical stimulus. Evidence indicates that secondary hyperalgesia reflects central sensitization, rather than pain per se.^{16,17} One study showed low intra-individual and high inter-individual variation of experimentally induced secondary hyperalgesia in males,¹⁸ suggesting that this measure could be reliable, but larger samples with both sexes are required.

Although pain intensity ratings are strongly associated with nociceptor discharge,¹⁹ pain reports can also be affected by acute and contextual biopsychosocial factors.^{20–23} Similarly, secondary hyperalgesia is associated with increased high-threshold heat-insensitive mechanoreceptor activity,²⁴ but can be modulated by pharmacological, neurostimulatory, and psychological manipulation.^{13,25,26} Therefore, the reliability and stability of pain outcome measures despite these acute day-to-day fluctuations must be established.

The present study aims to determine the test-retest reliability and stability of self-report pain intensity and pain unpleasantness ratings, as well as the extent of secondary hyperalgesia elicited by PHP in pain-free individuals across multiple sessions, over several days. All measures are hypothesized to show good to excellent test-retest reliability and be stable across sessions, based on the reliability of these measures in other experimental pain paradigms.^{3,6,18} The study further tests the reliability of pain intensity ratings to PHP from a previously collected independent sample.¹⁵ By comparing these measures over multiple sessions, the suitability of these measures can be determined for experimental pain studies occurring over several sessions, distributed over multiple days.

Materials and methods

Sample size determination

A sample size calculation for the reliability analyses was conducted with a web-based sample size calculator for intraclass correlation coefficients (ICC).²⁷ A minimum acceptable ICC value of 0.60 and an expected ICC value of 0.85 were selected based on previous QST studies finding good-to-excellent reliability.^{3, 6,18} Statistical power

was set to 0.8 at an alpha of 0.05 with three repetitions per participant and no dropouts. The analysis suggested a minimum sample size of 18 is required.

Additionally, a power analysis was conducted for the stability analyses with G*Power (Version 3.1) to determine the minimum sample size for a repeated measure, within factor design. As there was no a priori effect size, the power required to detect a medium effect size (Cohen's $f = 0.25$) was estimated, with 80% power with alpha = 0.05. The analysis indicated that a minimum of 12 participants were required. However, given the growing evidence for sex differences in pain,^{28–30} the sample size was doubled to 24 (12 males and 12 females) to ensure adequate power for sex-disaggregated analyses.

Participants

Twenty-seven participants met the inclusion criteria and consented to procedures approved by the University of Toronto's Human Research Ethics Board (Protocol #41856). Inclusion criteria for participants were being in good general health and between the ages of 18–40 years. Exclusion criteria were having persistent pain or pain-related discomfort in the past two months, scars or procedures that may affect the sensation on the non-dominant arm, neurological disorders, pregnancy or intention of getting pregnant, breastfeeding, and past or present chronic pain.

After consent, participants were further screened based on the following exclusion criteria: cognitive deficits (assessed using the Mini- Mental State Exam;³¹ scores < 28), depressive symptoms (assessed using the Beck Depression Inventory;³² scores > 21), or indication of suicidal ideation (> 1 on item 9), and 50/100 pain intensity rating (P_{50}) temperature > 48 °C (for safety purposes; see below). Three participants were excluded due to P_{50} temperatures being > 48°C. The final sample comprised twenty-four participants (12 males and 12 females).

Based on previous safety testing (personal communication), stimulations at 48°C must not exceed a 20 s duration within a 90 s period. Furthermore, a cumulative exposure was restricted to a maximum of 120 s per skin site.

Experimental design

Participants underwent three study sessions, with each session performed at least two days apart and completion of all sessions within two weeks (Fig. 1). In the first session, participants consented and completed questionnaires. Afterwards they underwent a stimulus familiarization procedure. Next, a calibration procedure to identify a stimulus that would elicit a P_{50} was performed. Finally, participants underwent the phasic heat pain (PHP) stimulation (see below) at P_{50} and provided ratings to each stimulus. Secondary hyperalgesia was measured at the end of the session (Fig. 1A). In the second and third sessions, the familiarization protocol, PHP stimulation at P_{50} (determined in Session 1) were conducted and secondary hyperalgesia was measured (Fig. 1B).

Heat stimuli

A thermal stimulation device (TCSII, QST.Lab, and Strasbourg, France) with a T11 probe was used to deliver thermal stimuli to participant's volar forearms. The probe has 10 stimulating surfaces that can be controlled in pairs. During stimulation, 8 of the 10 surfaces were used, creating a 3cm-by-3cm stimulation area.

Stimulus familiarization

Participants underwent a brief familiarization procedure with the thermal probe to acclimatize them with the thermal stimuli performed in the study. Familiarization consisted of three 10-second thermal stimuli delivered to the participant's dominant volar forearm in the following order: 45 – 43 – 47°C (Fig. 2). The ramp rate was set at 7°C/s from a baseline of 32°C, to deliver the target temperature for 5.5 s before returning to baseline at 7°C/s. The interstimulus interval was 15 s, where the probe was set to 32°C. During each stimulus, participants provided a pain intensity and a pain unpleasantness rating on a vNRS ranging from 0–100, with anchors 0 = not painful/not

Fig. 1. Experimental design outline. A) Participants first consent to the study and complete questionnaires. Afterwards they undergo the familiarization procedure and a P₅₀ temperature is determined. They are then stimulated at their P₅₀ temperature with the PHP protocol. Secondary hyperalgesia area is measured after P₅₀ stimulation. B) Participants undergo the familiarization procedure followed by the PHP protocol at their P₅₀. Secondary hyperalgesia area is measured after P₅₀ unpleasant and 100 = most painful imaginable/most unpleasant imaginable after the experimenter provided a verbal cue (“Rate Now”), three seconds after reaching the target temperature. If the participant felt that the stimulus

Stimulation.

Fig. 2. Familiarization protocol. Participants received three stimuli, one at 45°C, a second at 43°C and a third at 47°C. The stimulus had a rise and fall rate of 7°C/s and remained at the target temperature for 5.5 s before returning to a 32°C baseline temperature. The interstimulus interval was 15 s. Purple arrows indicate prompts to report pain intensity and unpleasantness. These prompts occurred 3 s after the target temperature was reached. If the stimulus was intolerable, they were instructed to say “Stop” and the program on the device was stopped and the thermal probe was removed from their arm.

Calibration of heat stimuli and P₅₀ determination

To determine the stimulation temperature, a stimulus intensity that elicited P₅₀ for each participant was identified. The perceptual intensity of the stimulus was matched, rather than the stimulus temperature, as this would allow for easier comparisons across participants, and higher inclusion rates in the study. To do so, the experimenter delivered a series of thermal stimuli (38°C, 39°C, 41°C, 43°C, 45°C, 47°C) to the participant’s dominant volar forearm in a pseudorandom fashion (Fig. 3). A sham stimulus (32°C) was included to ensure that the participant was providing ratings that reflected their true pain report. Each stimulus had a ramp and return rate of 2.5°C/s, where the stimulus remained at peak temperature for 20 s. The inter-stimulus interval was 10 s, where the probe returned to the baseline temperature of 32°C. During each stimulus, participants were prompted to provide a pain intensity and a pain unpleasantness rating (vNRS) 7 s after reaching the peak temperature with the cue of “Rate Now”. If participants did not report a value of 50 for pain intensity (allowance of vNRS between 40 and 60), additional stimuli were administered. In these cases, the experimenter calibrated the device to an appropriate temperature and administered the additional stimuli for 20 s each. The participant was instructed to provide pain intensity and pain unpleasantness ratings during the stimulus using the same verbal cue “Rate Now”. At this

stage, if stimuli $< 48^{\circ}\text{C}$ did not elicit a P_{50} rating, the participant was excluded for safety purposes. After each stimulus, the thermal probe was moved vertically on the volar forearm to avoid stimulating the same area of skin repeatedly. This calibration procedure was conducted only once during the first session. The P_{50} temperature determined in this initial session was then used in the subsequent sessions.

Phasic Heat Pain (PHP) application

The PHP model consists of five consecutive thermal stimuli at P_{50} for 40 s with a 20 s inter-stimulus interval (baseline of 32°C) with a ramp rate of $7^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{s}$ on the non-dominant volar forearm. This ramp rate was selected based on the fastest ramp rate used in a previous study,¹⁵ where the rise and fall times were fixed across participants, but the ramp rate was not. Here, fixing the ramp rate was important, and matched across participants. During each stimulation period, participants were asked their pain intensity and unpleasantness every 10 s, yielding 4 ratings per stimulation (Fig. 4). If the stimulation was deemed intolerable, participants were instructed to say “Stop” and the probe was removed from the forearm.

Of note, the distinction between phasic and tonic stimuli is not universally standardized; phasic stimuli are generally defined as brief

Fig. 3. Calibration of heat stimuli and P_{50} determination. Participants received twelve stimuli at range of temperatures ($32 - 47^{\circ}\text{C}$) in a pseudorandomized fashion. Each stimulus had a rise and return rate of $2.5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{s}$ and remained at the peak temperature for 20 s before returning to the baseline temperature of 32°C . The interstimulus interval was 10 s. Purple arrows indicate prompts to provide a pain intensity and a pain unpleasantness rating. These prompts occurred 7 s after the stimulus reached the peak temperature.

Fig. 4. Phasic Heat Pain (PHP) protocol. Participants received five thermal stimuli at their individually determined P_{50} temperature for 40 s with a 20 s interstimulus interval where the probe returned to the baseline of 32°C on their non-dominant volar forearm. The stimulus had a rise and return rate of $7^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{s}$. Purple arrows indicate prompts to provide a pain intensity and a pain unpleasantness every 10 s at P_{50} .

(ranging from milliseconds to several seconds), whereas tonic stimuli involve more sustained durations, often exceeding 30 s. The terminology aligns with Furman et al. (2020),¹⁵ who established this protocol, to ensure consistency across studies.

Secondary hyperalgesia area

To determine the area of secondary hyperalgesia, a 256 mN PinPrick Stimulator (MRC Systems, Heidelberg, Germany) was used along eight orthogonal lines radiating from the stimulation site (Fig. 5). Punctate stimulation

started 7 cm outside the stimulation site, moving in 0.5 cm steps towards the stimulation site, until the participant reports an increase of pain sensation. Once they reported the change in sensation, the border is marked. The procedure was repeated on a different trajectory until all eight trajectories were completed. Trajectories were marked on a digital map and the area was measured on ImageJ³³ in cm².

Reliability of pain intensity ratings to PHP presented >8 weeks apart A previously collected PHP dataset was leveraged, where

participants underwent PHP in two sessions, at least eight weeks apart.¹⁵ Specifically, the temperature was determined in a baseline visit, where participants underwent a calibration procedure (see Furman et al., 2020 for details) to identify a P₅₀ temperature. For participants for whom a P₅₀ could not be identified, a stimulation temperature of 48°C was utilized. The PHP stimulation comprised of five 40-s stimuli with a 20 s inter-stimulus interval. Participants reported pain using an electronic visual analog scale with a slider (Medoc Advanced Systems Ltd). The average pain rating during stimulation was used as the outcome measure.

Statistical analyses

Outcome measures

Statistical analyses were performed in SPSS v.28.0.1.1,³⁴ Prism v.10 for Mac (GraphPad, Boston, MA, USA), and JASP v.0.19.3.³⁵ The primary outcome measures in this study were the absolute ratings of pain intensity measured on the vNRS for PHP, absolute ratings of pain unpleasantness measured on the vNRS for PHP, and the

area of secondary hyperalgesia (in cm²) resulting from PHP, for each session. Frequentists statistics were conducted for all analyses, however, in cases of null

Fig. 5. Secondary hyperalgesia area map. The map has eight orthogonal vectors radiating from the 3cm-by-3cm stimulation site. Each vector has 14 dots where each dot indicates a 0.5 cm increment, with a total distance of 7 cm in each of the directions. Punctate stimulation starts from the farthest dot away from the stimulation site on one vector and moves towards the site until the participant an increase of pain sensation. This is then repeated for each of the eight vectors. Arrow indicates the direction of punctate stimulation. Created in BioRender. Moayedi, M. (2025) <https://BioRender.com/zi950qz>.

Findings, complementary Bayesian analyses were performed to determine the strength of evidence in favour of the null or alternative hypothesis.

Intraclass Correlation Coefficients (ICC)

A two-way random effect, absolute agreement, ICC model was used to assess the test-retest reliability for repeated measures of pain intensity, pain unpleasantness, and secondary hyperalgesia area across sessions. Reliability was evaluated for single measures with a 95% confidence interval report. Based on established guidelines by Koo (2016),³⁶ ICC values were interpreted as poor reliability (< 0.50), moderate reliability (0.50 – 0.75), good reliability (0.75 – 0.90), and excellent reliability (> 0.90). An ICC value was calculated for all outcome measures in the data collected in this study, as well as data from Furman et al. (2020).¹⁵

Spearman correlations

Spearman's rank-order correlations were performed to analyse the consistency of pain intensity ratings, pain unpleasantness ratings, and secondary hyperalgesia area across the three sessions. Correlations were conducted separately for pain intensity ratings, pain unpleasantness ratings, and secondary hyperalgesia area, examining the associations of these outcomes between Session 1 and Session 2, Session 1 and Session 3, and Session 2 and Session 3. Similarly, a Spearman correlation was performed for data from Furman et al. (2020)¹⁵ where participants received a PHP at P₅₀ at least 8 weeks apart.

PHP pain intensity and pain unpleasantness

A two-way repeated measures ANOVA was conducted to evaluate the effects of session (Session 1, Session 2, Session 3) and stimulation trial (Stimulation 1, Stimulation 2, Stimulation 3, Stimulation 4, Stimulation 5) on pain intensity and pain unpleasantness ratings. Assumptions of sphericity were assessed using Mauchly's test; when violated ($p < 0.05$), the degrees of freedom were corrected using Greenhouse-Geisser corrections when epsilon was (ϵ) < 0.75 or Huynh-Feldt correction when the epsilon was ≥ 0.75 . Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$, and post-hoc pairwise comparisons were conducted with Bonferroni adjustments.

Secondary hyperalgesia area

A one-way repeated measures ANOVA was conducted using frequentist and Bayesian statistical approaches to investigate whether secondary hyperalgesia area differed across experimental sessions. Assumptions of sphericity were assessed using Mauchly's test; when violated ($p < 0.05$), the degrees of freedom were corrected using Greenhouse-Geisser corrections when epsilon was < 0.75 or Huynh-Feldt correction when the epsilon was ≥ 0.75 . Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$ and post-hoc comparisons were performed using Bonferroni adjustments.

Bayesian statistics to evaluate the evidence for the null hypothesis

Statistical analyses were conducted with both frequentist and Bayesian frameworks to comprehensively evaluate the findings. The frequentist approach is based on the concept of probability as long-run frequency, which allows

the assessment of the likelihood of observing data under a pre-specified null hypothesis. In turn, this permits hypothesis testing through p-values and confidence intervals. However, a limitation of the frequentist framework is that non-significant p-values ($p > 0.05$) do not provide evidence for the null but rather suggest an absence of evidence against it (i.e., for the alternative hypothesis). Complementary Bayesian analyses were conducted for any null findings from the frequentist tests which allowed BFs to be obtained which measure the strength of evidence in favour of the null hypothesis.^{37,38}

Bayes factors (BF) were computed to quantify the evidence for the alternative (H_1) hypothesis over the null hypothesis (H_0); denoted by BF_{10} . The BF_{10} has set predetermined ranges for the strength of evidence for H_1 over H_0 : a $1 < BF_{10} < 3$ indicates anecdotal evidence for the H_1 ; $3 \leq BF_{10} < 10$ indicates moderate evidence for the H_1 ; $10 \leq BF_{10} < 30$ indicate strong evidence for the H_1 ; $30 \leq BF_{10} < 100$ indicates strong evidence; $100 \leq BF_{10}$ indicates extreme evidence for the H_1 . Evidence for the H_0 has similar ranges, however, they are measured as $1/BF_{10}$. Therefore, a $1 > BF_{10} > 1/3$ indicates anecdotal evidence for the null hypothesis, and so on.

Post hoc analyses

Post-hoc comparisons were performed, and posterior odds (BFs adjusted for multiple comparisons) were calculated for each comparison. Posterior odds were corrected for multiple testing by fixing to 0.5 the prior probability that the null hypothesis holds across all comparisons.³⁹ Individual comparisons are based on the default t-test with a Cauchy prior ($0, r = 1/\sqrt{2}$).

PHP P₅₀ temperatures

To determine if there were any sex differences in P₅₀ temperatures, an independent samples t-test was conducted. Data normality was first verified with a Shapiro-Wilk test; in cases of non-normality, a Mann-Whitney U test was conducted.

Results

Descriptive statistics

Pain intensity ratings, pain unpleasantness ratings, and secondary hyperalgesia area to a PHP stimulation at P₅₀ from three separate sessions across multiple days were compared. Table 1 provides a summary of the sample demographic. The final study sample consisted of 12 males (mean \pm SD age = 23.6 ± 3.3) and 12 females (23.3 ± 5.1). Demographic data from the Furman study can be found published elsewhere.¹⁵

Table 1

Participant demographics.

Age (years)	
Mean Age (SD)	23.5 (4.2)
Sex (# of participants)	
Male	12
Female	12
Gender (n)	
Man	12
Woman	12
Other	0
Race (n)	
East Asian	8

South Asian	3
Southeast Asian	1
Latin American	1
Middle Eastern	2
White/European	9
Religion or Spiritual Affiliation (n)	
Atheism	1
Christianity	3
Christian Orthodox	1
Hinduism	1
Islam	2
No spiritual or religious affiliation	16

Secondary hyperalgesia area exhibits greater reliability than pain intensity and pain unpleasantness ratings. A two-way random effects ICC model was conducted to determine the reliability of pain intensity, pain unpleasantness, and secondary hyperalgesia area across sessions (Table 2). The PHP pain intensity ICC for single measures was 0.755 (95% CI: 0.554 – 0.880), indicating good reliability. An F-test showed that the reliability is statistically significant $F_{23, 46} = 12.69, p = 4.6 \text{ e-}13$. The PHP pain unpleasantness ICC for single measures was 0.636 (95% CI: 0.322 – 0.825), indicating moderate reliability. An F-test showed that the reliability is statistically significant $F_{23, 46} = 9.47, p = 8.6 \text{ e-}11$. The secondary hyperalgesia area ICC for single measures was 0.840 (95% CI: 0.716 – 0.921), indicating good reliability. An F-test showed that the reliability is statistically significant $F_{23, 46} = 17.32, p = 1.2 \text{ e-}15$.

Pain intensity reliability validated in an independent sample

The ICC was calculated for pain intensity from a previous study,⁴⁰ where participants underwent a PHP stimulation calibrated to P₅₀ in two visits separated by eight weeks, on average (Table 3). The pain intensity ICC for single measures was 0.718 (95% CI: 0.572 – 0.821), indicating moderate reliability. A one-way ANOVA showed that the reliability is statistically significant ($F_{45, 45.5} = 6.00, p = 7.6 \text{ e-}9$).

Table 2

Intraclass correlation coefficients (ICC) of pain outcome measures to PHP, assessing the reliability of the ratings across the three visits.

Variable	ICC (95% CI)	F-Test (true value = 0)		
		F	df1, df2	p
PHP Pain Intensity	0.755 (0.554 – 0.880)	12.69	23, 46	4.6 e-13
PHP Pain Unpleasantness	0.636 (0.322 – 0.825)	9.47	23, 46	8.6 e-11
Secondary Hyperalgesia Area	0.840 (0.716 – 0.921)	17.32	23, 46	1.2 e-15

Abbreviations: CI = Confidence Intervals; df = degrees of freedom; ICC = Intraclass correlation; PHP = phasic heat pain

Table 3

Intraclass correlation coefficients (ICC) of pain intensity ratings to PHP, assessing the reliability of the ratings across the two visits 3-months apart.

Variable	ICC (95% CI)	F-Test (true value = 0)
F	df1, df2	p

Pain Intensity 0.719 (0.572–0.821) 6.00 45, 45.47 6 e-9 Abbreviations: CI = Confidence Intervals; df = degrees of freedom; ICC = Intraclass correlation; PHP = phasic heat pain

Pain outcome measures are positively and significantly correlated across sessions

Statistically significant positive correlations were observed across sessions for each of the pain outcomes: pain intensity, pain unpleasantness, and secondary hyperalgesia area. For pain intensity, Spearman’s correlation coefficients between sessions were $\rho = 0.79$ (Session 1 vs. Session 2), $\rho = 0.84$ (Session 2 vs. Session 3), and $\rho = 0.86$ (Session 3 vs. Session 1), all $p < 0.001$. For pain unpleasantness, correlations between sessions were $\rho = 0.78$ (Session 1 vs. Session 2), $\rho = 0.83$ (Session 2 vs. Session 3), and $\rho = 0.84$ (Session 3 vs. Session 1), all $p < 0.001$. For secondary hyperalgesia area $\rho = 0.81$ (Session 1 vs. Session 2), $\rho = 0.77$ (Session 2 vs. Session 3), and $\rho = 0.87$ (Session 3 vs. Session 1), all $p < 0.001$ (Fig. 6). Note correlations between pain outcome measures while controlling for days between sessions are in the Supplemental Materials (Table S1). Similarly, pain intensity ratings to PHP presented in two sessions, at least 8 weeks apart, showed a significant positive correlation ($\rho = 0.77$, $p < 0.001$; Table 4).

Session and stimulation trial significantly affect php pain intensity ratings

A frequentist two-way repeated-measures ANOVA was conducted to determine the effects of session and stimulation trial on pain intensity ratings. Mauchly's Test of Sphericity was not significant for session ($p = 0.207$). However, Mauchly’s test was significant for stimulation trial ($p < 0.001$) and the session-by-stimulation trial interaction ($p < 0.001$).

Thus, the degrees of freedom were corrected for stimulation trial ($\epsilon = 0.423$) and session-by-stimulation trial interaction ($\epsilon = 0.532$) using Greenhouse-Geisser estimate of sphericity.

The main effect of session ($F_{2,46} = 7.358$, $p = 0.002$, $\eta^2_p = 0.242$) and stimulation trial ($F_{1,693, 38.941} = 6.367$, $p = 0.006$, $\eta^2_p = 0.217$), on pain intensity ratings were significant. However, there was no significant session-by-stimulation trial interaction ($F_{4,254, 97.847} = 0.592$, $p = 0.680$, $\eta^2_p = 0.025$ Greenhouse-Geisser corrected). For the main effect of session, post hoc comparisons with Bonferroni correction showed that pain intensity ratings in Session 1 were significantly higher than in Session 3

Table 4

Correlation of PHP pain intensity ratings for each session from Furman 2020.

Session Pair	Pain Outcome Measure	ρ	df	p
1 vs 2	Pain Intensity	0.77	44	<0.001

Correlation coefficients (r), significance (p), and degrees of freedom (df) for comparisons between Session 1 and Session 2 pain intensity ratings.

Fig. 6. Spearman's correlations of outcome measures between sessions. Each panel displays the relationship between pairs of sessions. Lines represent the best-fit linear regression with 95% confidence intervals.

($p = 0.004$; Fig. 7A).

For the main effect of stimulation trial, post hoc comparisons with Bonferroni correction showed that pain intensity ratings were significantly higher for Stimulation 1 compared to Stimulation 2 ($p = 0.002$), Stimulation 4 had significantly higher pain intensity ratings compared to Stimulation 2 ($p = 0.023$) and Stimulation 3 ($p = 0.010$), and Stimulation 5 had significantly higher pain intensity ratings compared to Stimulation 2 ($p = 0.028$) and Stimulation 3 ($p = 0.027$; Fig. 7B).

Session and stimulation trial significantly affect PHP pain unpleasantness ratings

A frequentist two-way repeated measures ANOVA was conducted to determine the effects of session and stimulation trial on pain unpleasantness ratings. Mauchly's Test of Sphericity was not significant for session ($p = 0.425$). However, Mauchly's test was significant for stimulation trial ($p < 0.001$) and the session-by-stimulation trial interaction ($p < 0.001$). Thus, the degrees of freedom were corrected for stimulation trial ($\epsilon = 0.371$) and session-by-stimulation trial interaction ($\epsilon = 0.422$) using Greenhouse-Geisser estimate of sphericity.

The main effect of session ($F_{2,46} = 8.658$, $p < 0.001$, $\eta^2_p = 0.273$) and stimulation trial ($F_{1.482, 34.095} = 4.600$, $p = 0.026$, $\eta^2_p = 0.167$), on pain unpleasantness ratings were significant. However, there was no significant session-by-stimulation trial interaction ($F_{3.375, 77.625} = 0.904$, $p = 0.452$, $\eta^2_p = 0.038$).

For the main effect of session, Bonferroni-corrected post hoc comparisons showed that pain unpleasantness ratings in Session 1 were significantly higher than Session 3 ($p < 0.001$; Fig. 8A).

For the main effect of stimulation trial, Bonferroni-corrected post hoc comparisons showed that pain unpleasantness ratings were significantly higher in Stimulation 1 compared to Stimulation 2 ($p = 0.004$), Stimulation 4 had significantly higher pain unpleasantness ratings compared to Stimulation 3 ($p = 0.046$), and Stimulation 5 had significantly higher pain unpleasantness ratings compared to Stimulation 3 ($p = 0.045$; Fig. 8B).

Session has no significant effect on secondary hyperalgesia area

A one-way repeated measures ANOVA was conducted to determine the effect of session on secondary hyperalgesia area. Mauchly's Test of Sphericity was not significant for session ($p = 0.425$), thus no correction was applied.

The main effect of session was not significant ($F_{2,46} = 1.250$, $p = 0.296$, $\eta^2_p = 0.052$). A complementary one-way repeated measures Bayesian ANOVA revealed moderate evidence against a main effect of session ($BF_{10} = 0.297$) on secondary hyperalgesia area. Post-hoc comparisons with posterior odds provided moderate evidence against a difference between Session 1 and 2 (odds of $1/0.27 \approx 3.70$) and between Session 2 and 3 (odds of $1/0.127 \approx 7.87$). However, there was anecdotal evidence against a difference of between Session 1 and Session 3 (odds of $1/0.345 \approx 2.90$; Fig. 9).

No significant differences in P₅₀ temperature between sexes

A Mann-Whitney U test was performed to compare the P₅₀ temperature values for males and females. Median P₅₀ temperatures for males and females were 44.8°C (IQR = 43.9°C – 46.0°C) and 45.5°C (IQR = 43.4°C – 47.1°C), respectively. There was no statistically significant difference in P₅₀ temperatures between males and females ($U = 63$, $p = 0.622$). Table 5 provides a summary of P₅₀ temperature ranges and medians. Note that sex disaggregated analyses are provided in Supplementary Materials (Figure S1-S4).

Discussion

The aim of this study was to determine the test-retest reliability and stability of subjective and objective pain outcome measures in response to PHP in pain-free individuals across multiple sessions. Self-report pain outcome

measures comprised vNRS for pain intensity and pain unpleasantness, and the objective measure comprised of the area of secondary hyperalgesia elicited by PHP. The hypothesis that there would be good-to-excellent reliability and stability across all pain outcome measures (based on previous studies employing other pain models^{5, 41-44}) was not borne out: findings show that pain intensity and pain unpleasantness ratings have moderate-to-good ICC values and strong positive correlations across sessions. Further exploration of the reliability of PHP pain intensity ratings from a previous study by Furman et al. (2020),¹⁵ where measurements were at least 8-weeks apart, found strong positive correlations between sessions and moderate reliability. Together, these data show support for the moderate-to-good reliability of self-report pain outcome measures to PHP across multiple sessions. Conversely, secondary hyperalgesia area was not affected by the session, with ICC

Fig. 7. PHP protocol pain intensity ratings across sessions and stimulations. (A) Mean pain intensity ratings across sessions. Connecting lines represent paired ratings for each participant across sessions for each stimulation. (B) Mean pain intensity ratings across stimulations. Connecting lines represent paired ratings for each participant across stimulations for each session. (Verbal numerical rating scale; vNRS). * < 0.05, ** < 0.01.

Fig. 8. PHP protocol pain unpleasantness ratings across sessions and stimulations. (A) Mean pain unpleasantness ratings across sessions. Connecting lines represent paired ratings for each participant across sessions for each stimulation. (B) Mean pain unpleasantness ratings across stimulations. Connecting lines represent paired ratings

for each participant across stimulations for each session. (Verbal numerical rating scale; vNRS). * < 0.05, ** < 0.01.

Fig. 9. Secondary hyperalgesia area across sessions. Each dot represents a participant’s secondary hyperalgesia area (cm²) for the session and each line represents one participant's data across sessions. Bars indicate the mean value for each session. Ns = non-significant (p > 0.05). BF = corrected Bayes Factor for multiple comparisons against a difference.

Values demonstrating good reliability. This suggests that there is a dissociation between subjective pain perception and stimulus-induced central sensitization. Findings also show that subjective pain outcome ratings were not stable across stimulations, within a session, or between sessions.

The reliability analyses showed that self-report measures had lower

Table 5

P₅₀ temperatures used during PHP and temperature range. There was no significant difference between sexes (U = 63, p = 0.622).

PHP Temperature	Median (IQR)	Range
Males	44.8°C (43.9°C; 46.0°C)	42.0 – 47.0°C
Females	45.5°C (43.4°C; 47.1°C)	38.0 – 47.3°C
All Subjects	46.1°C (43.5°C; 47.0°C)	38.0 – 47.3°C

Reliability than hypothesized, as they had into the moderate-to-good range, across two different datasets. Previous findings show that outcome measures for experimental pain models vary in reliability.^{8,12, 43,44} Furthermore, previous research using PHP showed that pain ratings were stable over time and not significantly altered by the introduction of a tonic stimulus between phasic stimulations.¹¹ Systematic reviews report that the

reliability of thermal QST measures depends on the methodology used, specifically heat pain thresholds had greater reliability (fair to good) than warm detection thresholds (fair).¹⁰ These other studies had much larger sample sizes than the current study, and thus may have had substantially more variance that could drive observed differences in reliability. Additionally, the physiological pain measure of secondary hyperalgesia area had greater reliability than the self-report measures, which had good reliability. Together with previous studies, self-report pain rating to heat pain paradigms vary significantly, depending on the paradigm. Moreover, secondary hyperalgesia area remained stable, demonstrating that this physiological marker may be a more suitable measure of pain sensitivity—at least in conjunction with self-report pain ratings.

The decrease in pain intensity and pain unpleasantness ratings within and between sessions could be due to the reduced pain sensitivity or reduced novelty, nervousness, or anticipatory effects that are usually present in the first session, and typically dissipate upon repeated exposure. In this context, the decrease in pain ratings is attributed to repeated exposure to the paradigm; since the stimulus was calibrated for each participant at baseline and remained constant across sessions, the reduction in perceived pain was not due to changes in the stimulus itself. Previous studies have reported a similar pattern of within session pain reduction. To mitigate this effect, a familiarization paradigm was employed, but this did not seem to have the desired impact. It plausible that such effects may be related to habituation from repeated stimulation on the same site.⁴⁵

The session-dependent finding is consistent with prior research which demonstrated between-session reduction in self-report pain report in response to repeated heat stimuli.^{46–48} A study found that the decrease of pain ratings across sessions may be influenced by psychological factors :⁴⁷ higher trait anxiety was associated with smaller pain report decreases across sessions. This supports the notion that as participants became more familiar with the experimental procedure their anxiety and apprehension is reduced. This reduction in negative emotional valence can directly influence the perceived pain experience across sessions.⁴⁹ These findings indicate a crucial top-down influence on the subjective pain experience, facilitating the responses to persistent stimuli.

While subjective pain measures in the PHP paradigm showed a steady decrease across sessions, secondary hyperalgesia area was observed to be stable. This was further supported by Bayesian statistics, which found moderate evidence against the effect of session. The contrasting stability of both pain outcome measures suggests that they are governed by distinctive underlying mechanisms. Central sensitization is thought to be the neuroplastic change in the central nervous system, resulting in increased excitability in the spinal dorsal horn neurons.^{16,50, 51} Although secondary hyperalgesia is not a direct measure of central sensitization, evidence indicates that it is the behavioural proxy of this physiological phenomenon.^{16,17,52–54} Previous findings have shown that secondary hyperalgesia is modifiable through targeted pain-focused interventions,²⁶ but this study suggests that the measure is stable in the absence of such intervention.

The instability of subjective pain outcome measures across sessions, despite the relatively small sample size compared to other such studies, indicates a larger effect size, and thus has implications for the use of thermal QST in interventional studies. When subjective pain outcome measures change across session in the absence of intervention, it is difficult to discern whether a post-intervention pain outcome change is due to the intervention or session-to-session variance. To address these limitations, future research must incorporate a sham arm to capture if the changes in outcome measures are due to the intervention or natural variation. Furthermore, employing counterbalanced designs and the use of multiple, complementary outcome measures would mitigate order effects and provide a more accurate reflection of pain sensitivity.

A distinct pattern of pain intensity and pain unpleasantness report was discovered across the stimulation trials in the PHP protocol. Specifically, there was a decrease of pain report after the first stimulus which was then followed by an increase for the remaining stimulations. Furman et al. (2020) found a similar pattern of pain ratings, where they attributed the decrease of pain report from the first to the second trial to the elevated salience of the first stimulation and had a linear increase of pain report for the subsequent trials. The pattern was also reported in other repetitive thermal pain models,⁵⁵ reinforcing the utility of this PHP model as a prolonged pain paradigm used in future studies.

Although sex differences were not a focus of the study, given the evidence of sex differences in pain,^{28–30} further exploration was conducted to determine whether there were sex differences in the three pain outcome measures. This study found that the observed differences in subjective pain outcome measures were driven by male participants. However, consistent with the main results, there was no difference in secondary hyperalgesia area across sessions in both sexes. There are mixed findings with regard to sex differences in the reliability of pain reports to heat stimulation, as some studies show that the effect is driven by males,⁸ whereas others show no sex differences.⁵⁶ The greater decrease in pain report to the stimulus across the sessions in the current study may be driven by various factors such as expectation of gender roles and the endocrine system.^{57,58} However, it is beyond the scope of the current study to determine what may be driving these sex differences in the subjective pain outcome measures, and future studies must identify these factors.

Pain is a complex biopsychosocial phenomenon; thus, one's pain experience is not only shaped by the nociceptive input but also factors such as mood, belief, and coping strategies.^{59–61} These components can be captured through self-report questionnaires. However, in the present study detailed questionnaires were not collected across all session days. Consequently, potential day-to-day factors such as mood and anxiety that could influence the participants pain perception are unable to be investigated,^{60,62} as previously shown through the induction of negative mood which resulted in heightened affective pain ratings.^{63–65} Future research should integrate a more comprehensive assessment of these variables to gain a more complete understanding of their impact on pain responses.

In sum, the present study investigated the reliability and stability of pain outcome measures in healthy individuals across multiple sessions on separate days. Self-report pain intensity and pain unpleasantness were found to have moderate-to-good reliability. Additionally, these subjective pain ratings decreased across sessions demonstrating instability of these ratings—an effect driven by males. In contrast, the area of secondary hyperalgesia, a behavioural proxy for central sensitization, demonstrated greater reliability than subjective pain ratings and remained stable across sessions. Furthermore, a distinct pattern of pain ratings was found that was also observed by Furman et al. and other repetitive thermal pain models. Future research should investigate further how these biopsychosocial factors influence the day-to-day subjective pain ratings and sensory patterns of individuals to experimental heat pain across multiple days.

References

- Raja, S. N., Carr, D. B., Cohen, M., et al. (2020). The revised International Association for the Study of Pain definition of pain: Concepts, challenges, and compromises. *Pain*.
- Jensen, M. P., & Karoly, P. (1992). Self-report scales and procedures for assessing pain in adults. In *Handbook of pain assessment* (pp. 135–151). Guilford Press.

- Ferreira-Valente, M. A., Pais-Ribeiro, J. L., & Jensen, M. P. (2011). Validity of four pain intensity rating scales. *Pain*, 152(10), 2399–2404.
- Williamson, A., & Hoggart, B. (2005). Pain: A review of three commonly used pain rating scales. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 14(7), 798–804.
- Alghadir, A. H., Anwer, S., Iqbal, A., & Iqbal, Z. A. (2018). Test-retest reliability, validity, and minimum detectable change of visual analog, numerical rating, and verbal rating scales for measurement of osteoarthritic knee pain. *Journal of Pain Research*, 11, 851–856.
- Price, D. D., McGrath, P. A., Rafii, A., & Buckingham, B. (1983). The validation of visual analogue scales as ratio scale measures for chronic and experimental pain. *Pain*, 17(1), 45–56.
- Euasobhon, P., Atisook, R., Bumrungchatudom, K., Zinboonyahgoon, N., Saisavoey, N., & Jensen, M. P. (2022). Reliability and responsivity of pain intensity scales in individuals with chronic pain. *Pain*, 163(12), e1184–e1191.
- Amir, C., Rose-McCandlish, M., Weger, R., et al. (2022). Test-retest reliability of an adaptive thermal pain calibration procedure in healthy volunteers. *Journal of Pain*, 23(9), 1543–1555.
- Chong, P. S., & Cros, D. P. (2004). Technology literature review: Quantitative sensory testing. *Muscle & Nerve*, 29(5), 734–747.
- Moloney, N. A., Hall, T. M., & Doody, C. M. (2012). Reliability of thermal quantitative sensory testing: A systematic review. *Journal of Rehabilitation Research and Development*, 49(2), 191–207.
- Granot, M., Sprecher, E., & Yarnitsky, D. (2003). Psychophysics of phasic and tonic heat pain stimuli by quantitative sensory testing in healthy subjects. *European Journal of Pain*, 7(2), 139–143.
- Vincenot, M., Beaulieu, L. D., Gendron, L., Marchand, S., & Leonard, G. (2024). Reliability and minimal detectable change of dynamic temporal summation and conditioned pain modulation using a single experimental paradigm. *PLoS One*, 19(7), e0307556.
- Absy, S. S., Osborne, N. R., Osokin, E. E., et al. (2024). It's the sound, not the pulse: Peripheral magnetic stimulation reduces central sensitization through auditory modulatory effects. *bioRxiv*.
- Furman, A. J., Prokhorenko, M., Keaser, M. L., et al. (2024). Prolonged pain reliably slows peak alpha frequency by reducing fast alpha power. *eLife Sciences Publications, Ltd.*
- Furman, A. J., Prokhorenko, M., Keaser, M. L., et al. (2020). Sensorimotor peak alpha frequency is a reliable biomarker of prolonged pain sensitivity. *Cerebral Cortex*, 30(12), 6069–6082.
- Treede, R. D., Meyer, R. A., Raja, S. N., & Campbell, J. N. (1992). Peripheral and central mechanisms of cutaneous hyperalgesia. *Progress in Neurobiology*, 38(4), 397–421.